

Spectrophotometric Studies on Some Hydroxy Azocompounds in Organic Solvents of Varying Polarities and in Buffer Solutions.

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The uv and visible spectra of some hydroxy azocompounds of increasing fused benzene rings are investigated in organic solvents of varying polarities in relation to molecular structure and polarity of the medium. The spectra are studied in aqueous buffer solutions and in buffer solutions containing 30% dioxane. The variation of absorbance with pH is utilised for the determination of pK values of the compounds. The effects of substituent λ_{max} and pK are also studied.

THE absorption spectra of azobenzene and its derivatives have been the subject of some investigations¹⁻³, the bands observed were shown to be due to $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions¹. The weak $n-\pi^*$ transitions of azobenzene in acid medium were assigned to separate n_a and n_b levels of the two n_s electrons.

Toku Vyemura⁹ found that absorption bands in the spectra of hydroxy azocompounds are generally red shifted with increasing pH. Ufimtsev¹³ showed that the insolubility of azocompounds, e.g. 1-phenyl-azo-2-naphthol in alkalies-is due to their limited solubility in water.

The present work deals with the spectrophotometric studies of some hydroxy azobenzenes and their SO_3H derivatives containing fused benzene rings in organic solvents of varying polarities, in aqueous solutions and aqueous solutions containing 30% dioxane. It is attempted to clarify the effect of molecular structure on the spectral behaviour of the compounds.

Experimental

Azo compounds were prepared according to the method of Kamel¹⁴. The structure of the compounds studied is shown in Table 1. $10^{-4} M$ stock solutions were prepared by dissolving the accurate weight of the compound in the appropriate volume of the required solvent. For measurements in buffer solutions, due to low solubility of the compounds in water and alkali¹¹, freshly prepared solutions were obtained by dissolving the compound in 30% dioxane. The sulphonated derivatives were dissolved in redistilled water.

The universal buffer solutions of pH 2-12 were prepared as reported by Britton¹⁵. The pH's of the solutions were checked using a radiometer pH meter model 28 accurate to ± 0.05 units.

The absorption spectra in the uv and visible regions were recorded on a Zeiss spectrophotometer using 1.0 cm matched silica cells.

The compounds investigated are 1-hydroxy-2-phenyl azo-naphthalene(I), 2-hydroxy-1-phenyl azo naphthalene(II), 9-hydroxy-10-phenyl azo acenaphthene(III), 5-hydroxy-6-phenyl azo chrysenes(IV) and 6-hydroxy-5-phenyl azo chrysenes and their para sulphonated derivatives.

Results and Discussion

I-Spectra in Organic Solvents :

It is clear from the spectra of the compounds investigated (Table 1, Fig. 1) that both λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} of the absorption bands are readily influenced by the nature of the solvent. The electronic absorption spectra of the compounds are composed of two sets of bands. The uv bands correspond to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the aromatic system. The other bands appearing in the visible region may be ascribed to the excitation of the π -electrons of the azo group influenced by charge

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ I in different organic solvents. a-Ethyl alcohol, b-ether, c-chloroform, d-Dioxane, e-Carbon tetrachloride.

TABLE I— λ_{max} AND ϵ_{max} FOR SOME AZOCOMPOUND IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Compound No.	Ethyl alc.		Ether		CHCl ₃		Dioxane		CCl ₄	
	λ_{max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	λ_{max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	λ_{max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	λ_{max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$	λ_{max}	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$
I	230	21.5								
	256									
	312	8.5	320	S	315	4.25	310	8.0	315	10.0
	480	17.5	465	9.25	480	9.75	470	19.0	470	21.2
II	293	22.50			295	19.75			300	S
	360	14.50	350	20.0	360	12.00	355	11.25	355	6.75
	494	21.75	490	28.0	496	20.75	493	18.25	493	11.0
III	210	38.0								
	255	38.25								
	265	40.0					265	34.5		
	290	19.5	390	6.5			290	15.5	290	23.0
	480	30.5	470	22.75			480	24.0	475	24.5
IV	235	38.75					255	27.5		
	250	44.0			285	31.8	290	S	290	S
	335	5.75	340	6.75	340	7.5	340	6.5	340	4.0
	485	26.0	480	29.75	490	29.8	485	24.5	480	15.2
	505	S	500	30.75	510	30.0	510	25.0	510	15.5
V	225	22.75								
	270	34.0			275	S	270	33.0	275	S
	330	10.25	330	9.5	335	15.25	334	10.75	335	13.5
	395	5.75	400	S	405	S	395	S	405	S
	505	10.0	495	9.0	504	14.5	502	10.75	500	12.5

S=Shoulder

transfer originating from the OH-group and sinking in the phenyl ring, which can be represented as follows :

The effect of the polarity of the medium :

In general, the increase of the polarity of the medium, shifts the bands to higher wavelengths, i.e. in the order ethyl alcohol > ether > CHCl₃ > CCl₄, which shows that these bands are of the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition type^{1,6}.

1. The uv bands located near 312 nm in case of compound I or near 335 nm in the case of compounds IV and V, are blue shifted in ethanol relative to ether, although ethyl alcohol (26 D) is a solvent with relatively high polarity compared to ether (4.335 D). The blue shift in this $n-\pi^*$ transition band in alcohol relative to ether, results from H-bonding (the lone pair of electrons on azo nitrogen acts as an electron donor to the hydrogen of the solvent, which lowers the energy of n-orbital, and hence a blue shift in alcohol relative to ether,

2. The visible band (C.T. band) is slightly red shifted in alcohol relative to other solvents such as ether, CCl₄ and dioxane. This small red shift can be explained on the basis that the alcohol molecules associate with the OH-group through H-bond formation. This can readily occur through either the oxygen or hydrogen of the OH-group as follows :

(Compound I)

Such association leaves a negative charge on oxygen of the OH-group which in turn causes more delocalisation of electrons, i.e. requires lower energy and hence a red shift is observed in alcohol.

3. It is also worthy to mention that the C. T. band suffers a slight red shift in CHCl_3 (5.05 D) relative to ethyl alcohol. This may be due to the strong intermolecular hydrogen bond formed between the highly negative Cl-atom and the H-atom of the OH-group. However, the red shift of the visible band in alcohol or CHCl_3 supports the C. T. nature of this band.

The effect of molecular structure :

It is clear from Table 1, Fig. 2 that the increase in the number of fused benzene rings in the compounds investigated causes a red shift in the position of λ_{max} of the bands. This behaviour may be due to increasing conjugation through the whole molecule with increasing the number of benzene rings, i.e. more delocalisation of the π -electrons which in turn facilitates the excitation of these electrons and hence require lower energy and a red shift is attained.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of different azo compounds in ethyl alcohol I (a); II (b); III (c); IV (d); V (e).

II-Spectra in Buffer Solutions :

The visible absorption spectra of some of the compounds (nonsulphonated) investigated have been carried out in universal buffer solutions containing 30% dioxane in order to overcome the low solubility of these compounds in pure aqueous medium or dilute alkali¹³. The pK values obtained for these compounds and their p -sulphonated derivatives are depicted in Table 2. The spectra of compounds I, II and their p -sulphonated derivatives and p - SO_3H of compound III in aqueous buffers or containing 30% dioxane in solutions of low pH are characterised by an absorption band with λ_{max} located in the wavelength range 470–510 nm. This band is comparable to those observed in organic solvents and is mainly due to absorption by species with nonionised OH-group. On increasing the pH of the medium, the band becomes broad and exhibits a red shift as a result of the partial ionisation of the OH-group (cf. Fig. 3). This behaviour is due to the strong intramolecular H-bond formed between the ortho-OH group and the lone pair of electrons of the azo group¹¹. The spectra of these compounds also exhibit an isosbestic point (Fig. 3), denoting the existence of an equilibrium,

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of I p - SO_3H in buffer solutions containing 30% dioxane. a— pH 13.0, b— pH 11.87, c— pH 11.56, d— pH 11.23, e— pH 9.6, f— pH 8.82, g— pH 7.6, h— pH 5.5.

TABLE 2— pK VALUES OF SOME HYDROXY AZO COMPOUNDS AND THEIR p -SULPHONATED DERIVATIVES ($5 \times 10^{-5} M$)

Compound	Medium	pK -values			
		1st method	2nd method	3rd method	Mean
I I(p - SO_3H) I(p - SO_3H)	30% dioxane	11.35	11.40	11.61	11.38
	30% dioxane	11.18	11.18	11.19	11.18
	Aqueous-buffer	11.05	11.06	11.05	11.05
II II(p - SO_3H) II(p - SO_3H)	30% dioxane	11.25	11.25	11.20	11.25
	30% dioxane	10.35	10.30	10.40	10.35
	Aqueous	9.70	9.60	9.70	9.65
III III(p - SO_3H) III(p - SO_3H)	30% dioxane	11.30	11.30	11.35	11.30
	30% dioxane	11.15	11.20	11.18	11.20
	Aqueous	11.10	11.10	11.13	11.10

essentially an acid-base between ionised and nonionised forms :

III—Determination of pK :

The variation of absorbance with pH is utilised for the determination of the acid dissociation constants of the compounds. For this purpose three different methods are applied :

i—*Half-wave Height*¹⁷ : This method depends on the principle that pK is equal to the value of pH at which the two equilibrium species exist in equivalent quantities, i.e. at half-length of the A- pH curve.

$$pK = pH \text{ at } A_{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$A_{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\frac{A_{max} - A_{min}}{2} \right) + A_{min} \quad \dots(1)$$

where A_{max} and A_{min} are the maximum and minimum absorbances on the A- pH curve.

ii—*The limiting absorbance method*¹⁷ : This method makes use of the following relation :

$$pH = pK + \log \left(\frac{A}{A_{max} - A} \right) + \log \bar{v}$$

The pK values determined by this method are low in some cases due to partial overlap of absorption bands leading to high background. This does not allow attainment of a low A_{min} value on the A- pH curve. The error due to interference of the different species can be eliminated by using the following relation¹⁸.

$$pH = pK + \log \bar{v} + \log \frac{A_2 - A_1}{A_3 - A_2}$$

in which A_1 and A_3 are the absorbances in media containing either HL or L^- species only, A_2 and A_2' the absorbances in solutions where HL and L^- coexist.

iii—*The modified Collector method*¹⁹, as applied for the determination of the dissociation constants of weak acids²⁰, for this method :

$$K = \frac{C_{H_2^+} - C_{H_3^+}}{M - 1}$$

where

$$M = \left(\frac{A_3 - A_1}{A_2 - A_1} \right) \left(\frac{C_{H_1^+} - C_{H_3^+}}{C_{H_1^+} + C_{H_3^+}} \right)$$

A_1 , A_2 and A_3 are the absorbances at $C_{H_1^+}$, $C_{H_2^+}$ and $C_{H_3^+}$ respectively. The pK values obtained are shown in Table 2.

It is obvious that the pK values for the p -sulphonated derivatives are lower than those for the nonsulphonated compounds. This can be ascribed to the -M effect of the sulphonic group which leads to a weakening of the intramolecular H-bond. This latter causes in turn easier liberation of the proton of the OH-group and hence lower pK values.

For compounds IV, V and their p -sulphonated derivatives, the spectra are very little influenced by increasing the pH of the medium and hence the dissociation constants of these compounds are difficult to obtain.

From Table 2, it is obvious that in case of I and its sulphonic derivative, the difference between their pK -values is lower than between II and its sulphonic derivative. This is probably due to decreased H-bonding in compound II which lowers the ionisation than in compound I.

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